

Dissociation Constants of Ferrous-*tris*-dipyridyl Complex in *t*-butanol + H₂O Mixtures

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Manuscript received 2 September 1980, revised 4 May 1981, accepted 11 May 1981

The dissociation constants of ferrous-*tris*-dipyridyl complex have been determined in various *t*-butanol+H₂O mixtures to study the effect of solvents and ion-solvent interactions on the dissociation constants. The difficulties associated with the determination in different solvents have been outlined.

THE role of solvents on the dissociation constants of the metal complexes in solution has been relatively unexplored. In order to study the different factors affecting the stability constants of complexes and ion-solvent interactions, it is imperative to study the complexes in different solvents of varying dielectric constants and chemical nature.

Hazra and Lahiri^{1,2} studied the dissociation constants of ferrous-*tris*-dipyridyl complex (Ferrodiiin³) in different mixed solvents (aqueous methanolic and aqueous ethanolic solutions) so as to get information regarding the effect of solvents on the equilibrium constants of

t-Butanol is known for its marked anomalous behaviour compared to methanol and ethanol. The result for the reaction (1) has been recently reported^{3,4} and we present in this communication, the results of our study of the ferrodiiin in different *t*-butanol+H₂O mixtures.

Experimental

t-BuOH (SD's Labgrade) was purified in the same way as described before⁴. The weight percentages and the dielectric constants were determined in the same way as described before⁴.

Most of the experimental details are given elsewhere^{1,2}. The molar absorptivities (ϵ) of ferrodiiin were determined from the measurements of O.d.'s of solutions containing 16-25 fold excess of ligand to different concentrations of Fe²⁺ at 520 nm and 530 nm. The molar absorptivities in different percentages of mixed solvents are given in Table 1.

For the determination of the stability constants, O.d.'s of solutions containing different concentrations of ferrous ion and dipyridyl were measured at 520 nm and 530 nm. Measurements were made at 25°. The H⁺ ion concentrations ranged between $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $6.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

TABLE 1—EXTINCTION CO-EFFICIENTS OF FERRODIIIN COMPLEX AT DIFFERENT PERCENTAGES OF *t*-BuOH-H₂O MIXTURES

Percentages of <i>t</i> -BuOH by weight	Extinction coefficients at 520 nm	Extinction coefficients at 530 nm
8.0	9817 (± 14)	8450 (± 50)
16.8	9496 (± 17)	8590 (± 32)
25.0	9305 (± 81)	8484 (± 27)
34.2	9395 (± 33)	8601 (± 47)
43.8	9647 (± 35)	8784 (± 59)
54.0	9472 (± 25)	8808 (± 54)
64.5	9432 (± 26)	8686 (± 45)
75.8	9652 (± 29)	8739 (± 36)

The average values of the concentrations of the complexes obtained from the o.d. readings at 520 and 530 nm and known values of the extinction coefficients were utilised to calculate the equilibrium constants.

The spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Beckman DU 2 spectrophotometer maintained at 25°.

Results and Discussion

The purpose of the present investigation is to understand the role of the solvents on the thermodynamic stability constants of the complexes and the proper understanding of the 'medium effect'. The determination of the thermodynamic stability constants is extremely difficult particularly in mixed solvents.

In mixed solvents, the activity coefficients change due to (i) Salt effect (sf_1) and (ii) Medium effect (mf_1)⁵.

In view of the limitations of determining the thermodynamic dissociation constants using 'inert electrolytes', it is always preferable to use very dilute solutions so that the activity coefficients (sf_1) should be regarded to be unity and the salt effect may be eliminated i.e.,

$$sf_1 \rightarrow 1, \text{ i.e., } sf_{\text{Fe}^{2+}} = sf_{\text{FeDipy}_3^{2+}} \text{ and } sf_{\text{H}^+} = sf_{\text{DipyH}^+}$$

This enables us to study the 'medium effect'. The use of 'inert electrolytes' are carefully avoided

as the 'solute-solvent' interactions of unknown magnitude⁶ are likely to mask the 'medium effect' for the reaction actually studied. Moreover, the relative magnitudes of the different types of interactions, often reinforcing or cancelling each other, are difficult to estimate.

Addition of excess of neutral electrolyte in mixed solvents may complicate the situation due to the following reasons :

(1) Ion-association between the ions of the neutral electrolytes with reactants or among themselves leads to the reduction in the concentration of reactants in question and reduction in the ionic strength of the solution⁷.

(2) Extensive polarization of solvent molecules leads to a variation of microscopic and macroscopic dielectric constants of the solvent molecules⁷⁻⁹.

(3) Breakdown of the tetrahedral structure of water and reduction in the concentration of solvent molecules take place due to the addition of alcohol. Further, addition of neutral electrolytes leads to the alteration of solvent structure. There will be decrease in the effective concentration of the solvent molecules due to solvation of ions. The effect will be particularly large in solvents containing high percentages of organic solvents. Preferential solvation of ions also takes place.

These effects can be considerably reduced, though not completely eliminated, if we work with dilute solutions.

In view of the above facts, the present work has been carried out in dilute solutions (ionic strength were of the order $\sim 10^{-3}M$) so that K_o becomes equal to thermodynamic equilibrium constant K_a .

The thermodynamic equilibrium constants K_a for reaction (2) have been calculated from the appropriate K_T values for the reaction (1) and from the equations

$$[\text{Dipy H}^+] = [\text{Dipy}]_T - 3(\text{Fedipy}_3^{2+}) - (\text{Dipy})$$

$$pK_T = pH + \log \frac{[\text{Dipy H}^+]}{[\text{Dipy}]}$$

$$\text{and } (\text{Fe}^{2+})_{\text{free}} = (\text{Fe}^{2+})_{\text{Total}} - (\text{Fedipy}_3^{2+})$$

The measurement of the hydrogen ion concentrations in mixed solvents containing the complexes and dipyH^+ are difficult. We have calculated the H^+ ion concentrations in the solutions and compared it with the H^+ ion concentrations obtained from meter-readings after appropriate corrections in mixed solvents¹⁰⁻¹².

A few typical values of the equilibrium constants for the reaction (2) using calculated H^+ ion concentrations and the measured H^+ ion concentrations from pH-meter readings with appropriate corrections in ethanol + H_2O mixtures are presented for comparison².

Wt% of ethanol	K_a for reaction (2)	
	Using observed H^+ ion concn. after proper correction	Using calculated (H^+) ion concn.
0.0	$7.56(\pm 0.27) \times 10^{-5}$	$4.36(\pm 0.15) \times 10^{-5}$
8.0	$4.48(\pm 0.16) \times 10^{-5}$	$2.51(\pm 0.07) \times 10^{-5}$
16.4	$2.85(\pm 0.12) \times 10^{-5}$	$1.56(\pm 0.06) \times 10^{-5}$
25.3	$1.55(\pm 0.06) \times 10^{-5}$	$7.01(\pm 0.25) \times 10^{-6}$

The two sets of equilibrium constant values indicate the extent of deviations which one can have in such measurements. It is also known that the slight error in the measurement of H^+ ion concentration (in terms of $pH \pm 0.04$) will have profound effect on the K_a value and the error in K_a values will be about $\pm 50\%$ ². The differences are also expected as the corrected H^+ ion takes into account the changes in the 'medium effect' of H^+ ion to some extent, though some error may creep into the result from

(1) Liquid-junction potential of uncertain magnitude,

(2) Changes in the sensitivity of the glass electrode, and

(3) Solute-solvent interactions.

Moreover, use of concentration terms for H^+ ion is preferable as all other terms used in the calculations are expressed in terms of concentration. In view of the facts described above, we prefer to use the theoretically calculated H^+ ion concentrations.

The dissociation constants for the reaction (3) in different solvents are given by^{1,2}

$$K = K_a \times K_T^2$$

The results are given in Table 2.

The molar absorptivities of the complex are considerably higher in $\text{Bu}^t\text{OH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures compared to $\text{MeOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{EtOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures. The molar absorptivities show no systematic variation and cannot be correlated with other data obtained. It may be that the oscillator strengths are considerably changed in these solvent mixtures.

The results show that pK_a value for reaction (2) may show a slight decrease with the introduction of organic solvents but it gradually increases with increase in organic solvents i.e., ΔG_i is positive. The results indicate that Fedipy_3^{2+} and H^+ ions appear to be less stable in organic solvents compared to Fe^{2+} and dipyH^+ . The reaction is 'isoelectric' in character, the decrease in dielectric constant should have slight effect on the dissociation constants, the change in pK values must be due to change in solute-solvent interactions which should be fairly high. But it is to be noted that electrostatic contributions as well as the free-energy of transfer of neutral components are of great importance in determining the change in pK -values. The solvation of Fedipy_3^{2+} and dipyH^+ should be less than Fe^{2+} and H^+ ions. It is likely that the ions are solvated by organic solvents but the extent of solvation is unknown.

TABLE 2—COMPARATIVE STUDIES OF pK -VALUES OF IRON-DIPYRIDYL COMPLEXES FOR REACTIONS (1) TO (3) IN METHANOL-WATER (S_1), ETHANOL-WATER (S_2) AND *t*-BUTANOL-WATER (S_3) MIXTURES

Vol. % of alcohols	pK_T for reaction (1)			pK_8 for reaction (2)			pK for reaction (3)		
	S_1	S_2	S_3	S_1	S_2	S_3	S_1	S_2	S_3
0.0	4.48	4.48	4.48	4.86	4.86	4.86	17.77	17.77	17.77
10	4.40	4.20	3.83	4.67	4.60	4.27	17.87	17.20	15.76
20	4.25	4.04	3.57	5.14	4.81	4.85	17.89	16.98	15.06
30	4.15	3.91	3.29	5.38	5.15	4.61	17.78	16.89	14.48
40	4.01	3.72	3.17	5.25	5.10	4.66	17.22	16.26	14.17
50	3.88	3.48	2.97	5.36	5.22	4.67	17.85	15.66	13.58
60	3.60	3.20	2.80	5.87	5.55	5.10	16.17	15.15	13.50
70	3.92	3.10	2.62	5.66	5.40	5.59	15.52	14.70	13.25
80	3.15	2.89	2.36	5.59	5.54	5.79	15.04	15.21	12.87
90	3.04	2.79	—	5.94	5.28	—	15.06	15.60	—

The ΔpK_i values for the reaction (2) appears to be high compared to those for MeOH+H₂O and EtOH+H₂O mixtures. In case of reaction (2), Fedipy₃²⁺ may be assumed to be little solvated due to bigger ion-size parameter, the changes in pK -values should depend upon the solvational properties of Fe²⁺, H⁺ and dipyH⁺ and solubility of dipy in different mixed solvents, whereas in case of reaction (3), the changes in pK should depend on the solvational properties of Fe²⁺, Fedipy₃²⁺ and dipy. It has been found that ΔpK_T for (3) is usually high compared to ΔpK_T values in MeOH+H₂O and EtOH+H₂O mixtures. Probably this is due to greater solubility of dipy in Bu^tOH compared to MeOH and EtOH. Fedipy₃²⁺ is relatively unstable in Bu^tOH. The nature of solvation of Fe²⁺ ion in Bu^tOH may also be different.

A comparative study for the reactions (1) to (3) in MeOH+H₂O, EtOH+H₂O and Bu^tOH+H₂O mixtures is presented in Table 2. Since the bonds involved in all these cases are the same, the changes in pK -values naturally reflect the differences in solute-solvent interactions depending on the basicities, the dielectric properties and other properties of the solvents.

It is known that $\Delta pK_i = \Delta pK_{i(\text{el})} + \Delta pK_{i(\text{none})} + \Delta pK_{i(\text{neut})}$. But due to the absence of accurate values of the radii of ions and the limitations of the Born equation, accurate $\Delta pK_{i(\text{el})}$ values cannot be calculated. The $\Delta pK_{i(\text{neut})}$ values are also unknown.

Thus, no clear picture regarding $\Delta pK_{i(\text{none})}$ values could be obtained and the specific role of the solvents could not be clearly understood. For the 'isoelectric' reactions, however, $\Delta pK_{i(\text{el})}$ can be assumed to be almost constant as a first approximation throughout the solvent composition and ΔpK_T should thus represent $\Delta pK_{i(\text{none})}$ which is

governed by solute-solvent interactions. Comparison of the data thus gives an approximate measure of solute-solvent interactions in different solvents.

But it is hardly true as $\Delta pK_{i(\text{el})}$ for the forward reaction is not balanced by $\Delta pK_{i(\text{el})}$ for the backward reaction due to the differences in radii values of the ions and the effect cannot be neglected when the decrease in the dielectric constant is appreciable.

It is thus apparent that the proper understanding of the role of the solvents on the dissociation constants and their successful utilization necessitate systematic investigations of the different aspects of the solution chemistry.

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